

Restructuring Through Organizational Resilience During the Crisis Period: The Effects of Organizational Learning Capabilities on Product Innovation in Exporting Firms

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Abstract

Nowadays, competition, which is increasing under the influence of globalization, has caused enterprises to expand beyond their borders in order to survive. Increased global uncertainty and unexpected disruptive events foster the emergence of innovation while making organizations vulnerable. It is thought that enhanced "organizational learning capabilities" of enterprises in crisis environments, especially those caused by unexpected disruptive events such as pandemics, wars, or major economic crises, will positively impact their product innovation potential through the mediating and moderating effects of resilience capacity. The purpose of the current research was to make a contribution to the literature in the field by clarifying how the impact of "organizational learning capabilities" on "product innovation" varies according to "organizational resilience" during crisis periods, particularly in exporting firms that are greatly affected by volatile conditions, and to guide the development of these firms. To test the proposed conceptual model, a field research was done on employees of exporting enterprises operating un-

der the Istanbul Textile and Apparel Exporters' Association (ITKIB) in Istanbul province. Factor analysis, validity, reliability, and correlation analyses were done on the data using SPSS, whereas mediation and moderation analyses were performed in SPSS Process Macro V.4. The empirical findings obtained from the field research reveal that "organizational learning" significantly and positively impacts "product innovation", "organizational learning" positively impacts "organizational resilience", "organizational resilience" significantly and positively correlates with "product innovation", and "organizational resilience" does not moderate the impact of "organizational learning" on "product innovation", but has a full mediating effect.

Keywords: Organizational Learning, Organizational Resilience, Product Innovation, Dynamic Capabilities Theory, Crisis Management.

JEL Codes: M00, M1, M16, L21, O3

Citation: Çelik, D., & Koçak Özer, A. (2026). Restructuring through organizational resilience during the crisis period: The effects of organizational learning capabilities on product innovation in exporting firms. *Researches on Multidisciplinary Approaches (ROMAYA Journal)*, 2026(1).

1. Introduction

Nowadays, organizations established to operate in any sector or line of business have to compete to create value in their fields. Innovation is an extremely effective tool to successfully compete in strategic terms. The significance of the concept of innovation is strengthened by competition that increases with globalization and the world changing with rapidly developing technologies. These rapid advancements, which also cause changes in customer needs, necessitate organizations to innovate and offer novel products. It is impossible for organizations that seek to survive in a globally competitive environment to ignore customer needs. Research in the field of innovation has recently increased since managing innovation from a strategic perspective effectively increases the advantages it can provide in competition.

Studies conducted in both developed and developing economies to date have demonstrated that organizations that improve their organizational capabilities will achieve significant competitive advantages both today and in the future. Studies conducted in both developed and developing economies to date indicate that theorists argue that organizations that improve their organizational capabilities will gain significant competitive advantages both today and in the future (Teece et. al., 1997; Zahra, et al, 2006; Teece, 2007; Salunke et. al, 2011; Weerawardena & Mavondo, 2011; Huang et. al.,2012; Coşkun&Özyılmaz, 2016). In this regard, through strategic human resources management, enterprises can ensure the necessary coordination by organizing their "organizational learning capabilities" in a way to display superior performance and contribute to creating competitive advantages by exhibiting superior performance. This issue is especially important for exporting enterprises whose structures are both labor-intensive and rapidly changing with technological developments.

Organizations' capabilities and the added values they obtain directly and indirectly affect their ability to create a difference, expand the existing markets, or ensure sustainable competitive advantages in new markets. "Organizational learning capability" takes place among the most essential elements of competition in this era of rapidly changing environmental conditions and unpredictable crises. Among these capabilities, "organizational learning" is important since it facilitates and contributes to development and change, while "organizational resilience" is crucial since it ensures survival and continued play under all conditions. Furthermore, several researchers have stated that the impact of external crisis factors on organizational resilience, as well as elements such as resource reconfiguration and proactive adaptation mechanisms, have not been adequately addressed (He et al., 2023; Fiksel, 2006; McManus et.

al., 2008; Al, 2025). Numerous researches in the literature have indicated the significance of innovation together with organizational learning (Özdevecioğlu & Biçkes, 2015; Sünnetçioğlu, 2018; Migdadi, 2021; Örmeci&Öcal, 2023; Şeker et. al., 2024) and resilience (Akgün&Keskin, 2014; Garrido-Moreno et al., 2024). Moreover, domestic and international research has mostly focused on the effects of "organizational learning capability" on firm performance (Jiménez-Jiménez & Sanz-Valle, 2011; Kalmuk & Acar, 2016; Sevinç&Efe, 2018; Ghasemzadeh et. al,2019; Migdadi, 2021; Kozcu&Özmen, 2023) or its mediating effect on diverse variables (Kendir et. al, 2019; Örmeci&Öcal, 2023; Yaylacı et.al., 2024). However, no research has examined the role of "organizational resilience" in the effect of "organizational learning capabilities" on "product innovation". The current study is unique since it eliminates the said gap in the literature by concentrating on how the effect of "organizational learning capabilities" on "product innovation" varies by "organizational resilience" within the framework of dynamic capabilities theory. This theory enables organizations to maintain their competitive advantages, particularly during periods of uncertainty and crisis, through their processes of perception, capture, and transformation (Teece, 2007; Al, 2025,709). It is considered that the present work will make a contribution to the literature in this respect, as well as because the data were mostly collected during the pandemic, allowing for a clearer analysis of the situation within an enterprise during a crisis.

The study's theoretical section explains the concepts of "organizational resilience", "organizational learning", and "product innovation", and the relationships between the concepts above. The characteristics of this capability and the effects of "organizational resilience" on improving the "product innovation" performance of organizations are explained by establishing causal relationships. The methodology section presents the conceptual model of the research, the hypotheses formulated in line with this model, and the findings of the analyses performed to test these hypotheses. The final section includes recommendations for the industry and academia in accordance with the analysis results.

2. Conceptual Framework

2.1. Organizational Learning

"Organizational learning" is a construct enabling the development of organizations and also a necessity for them (Altıntaş, 2024, 459). Cyert and March (1963), Cangelosi and Dill (1965), and Argyris and Schoen (1978) conducted the first important studies in this field. Rapid growth has been observed in this field both in academia and in practice since the above-mentioned studies (Akgün et al., 2002, 57). In stu-

dies on “organizational learning”, different authors defined “organizational learning” in different ways. As specified by Argyris and Schoen (1978), “organizational learning” is associated with the experience gained from mistakes and aims to continuously expand the existing organizational knowledge base (Scribner et al., 1999, 131). According to Hedberg (1981), “organizational learning” refers to identifying novel approaches and understandings by developing a common understanding and conceptual schemes within the organization and among its members (Fiol & Lyles, 1985, 804). Huber (1991, 89) defined “organizational learning” as “the transfer of knowledge within the organization that will cause changes in employee behaviors.” Guns and Anundsen (1998) expressed organizational learning as the whole of employees' daily learning activities. On the contrary, Hodgkinson (2000) defined organizational learning” as “the accumulation of knowledge obtained by developing approaches that enable mutual learning among employees in an organization” (Besler & Tonus, 2017, 73). According to the definition by Hsu and Fang (2009), “organizational learning” is the ability to possess current information and process it (Kozcu & Özmen, 2023, 484). Therefore, researchers in the literature have not agreed on the definition of “organizational learning”, and the definitions focus on similar points.

The current work is based on Armstrong's definition of “organizational learning”. As indicated by Armstrong (2017), “organizational learning” is a process and “a coordinated systemic change through structural and cultural mechanisms that groups and individuals can access to build and utilize organizational memory and to improve long-term organizational capacity” (Armstrong, 2017, 202-203).

Concerning how learning occurs at the organizational level, Huber (1991) associated this activity with a four-stage process. Knowledge acquisition, information distribution, information interpretation, and organizational memory constitute the four stages (Ghasemzadeh et al., 2019, 291). The stage of knowledge acquisition, the first step of the “organizational learning” cycle, begins with the collection of information from internal and external sources and includes the acquisition of new knowledge (Huber, 1991, 100). It is necessary and sufficient for the acquired knowledge to be new to the organization (Durna, 2005, 75). At the stage of information distribution, the knowledge acquired is shared among various organizational departments and employees (Nawaz & Tian, 2022, 964). Thus, access to the acquired knowledge is provided to all employees, facilitating knowledge transfer among employees and different departments (Davenport et al., 1998, 46). The stage of information interpretation occurs when employees give meaning to the new knowledge acquired and distributed, transforming it into shared new knowledge within the organization (Jimé-

nez-Jiménez & Sanz-Valle, 2011, 409). The old and new knowledge of the enterprise are combined and systematized at the stage in question (Yıldırım, 2015, 152). Organizational memory, the “organizational learning” cycle's final stage, is related to the storage of the acquired systematic knowledge within the organization (Sözen, 2017, 74-75). Organizational memory is a concept related to how knowledge is embedded in the organization (Fiol & Lyles, 1985, 804). The “organizational learning” cycle is completed in this way.

2.1.1. Dimensions of organizational learning

Researchers have defined the sub-dimensions of “organizational learning capability” in different ways. The present study addressed “organizational learning” as a five-dimensional concept, as in the research by Chiva and Alegre (2009), in the form most commonly used in the literature. The above-mentioned sub-dimensions include experimentation, risk-taking, interaction with the external environment, dialogue, and participative decision-making, respectively (Ağraş & Kılınç, 2015, 61).

The experimentation dimension is regarded as the most important dimension impacting “organizational learning capability” (Chiva & Alegre, 2009, 326). The dimension in question is based on innovation and testing of new ideas. Experimentation involves questioning how work is done in the enterprise, seeking new ways to do things, and making changes to relevant processes (Onağ & Tepeci, 2016, 54).

The risk-taking dimension describes the ability to tolerate uncertainty, ambiguity, and errors (Kozcu & Özmen, 2019, 528). As Sitkin (1996) states, failure is a basic requirement for effective organizational learning. The significance of risk-taking and accepting mistakes brings about benefits, such as risk tolerance, directing attention to problems and trying to solve them, recognizing and interpreting problems easily, and diversity in organizational responses (Sitkin, 1996, 541).

It is possible to define **interaction with the external environment** as the scope of an organization's interaction and relations with the external environment. The environments where organizations operate and the characteristics of these environments, as well as organizations' efforts to evolve with the changing external environment, take an essential part in learning (Chiva & Alegre, 2009, 328).

The dialogue dimension refers to a collective inquiry into the communication and processes that constitute daily experience in organizational relationships. This dimension focuses on transforming the quality of shared thinking and the language used, on which all interactions are based (Querubin, 2011). Dialogue must be uninterrupted both within the or-

organizational units of which employees are a part and between these units for organizational learning to occur in organizations (Avcı et al., 2010, 98).

The dimension of **participative decision-making** describes the involvement of organizational members in decision-making processes. Through participative decision-making, the rate at which knowledge possessed by organizational members is revealed increases, which contributes to the organization's learning capacity (Ağraş, 2013, 75).

2.2. Organizational Resilience

The "organizational resilience" concept, which has arisen as an essential strategic step for successful competition in a business environment that is continuously changing nowadays (Garrido-Moreno et al., 2024:2), has been primarily studied in psychology and at the individual level in the field of social sciences (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011, 244). In management science, the concept of "organizational resilience" began to be studied with Meyer's work conducted in 1982 and Weick's work performed in 1993 (Annarelli & Nonina, 2016, 3). Researchers in different disciplines have highlighted the concept of resilience, expressing the ability to adjust to the altering external environment, as a possible framework for coping with turbulent circumstances, which ensures organizational development and innovation (Akgün & Keskin, 2014, 6918).

It is possible to divide definitions in the literature on "organizational resilience" into two categories (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011, 244). The first of these categories addresses the concept as it is used in physics. The advocates of this view state that "organizational resilience" is the ability of organizations to recover and resume their activities after unexpected and adverse situations that disrupt their activities (Van der Vegt et al., 2015, 973). The second category refers to organizations developing novel capabilities and creating new opportunities to adapt to any situation. The advocates of this view characterized "organizational resilience" as the ability to develop and put into practice positive and adaptive behaviors that act quickly to overcome situations faced by the organization with minimal pressure (Al-Ayed, 2019, 180). This usage is referred to as the transformational perspective (Kumbali, 2018, 59).

Hamel and Välikangas (2003) asserted that "organizational resilience" is usually regarded as a desirable organizational property to cope with diverse adversities during turbulent times (Ma et al., 2018, 247). Burnard and Bhamra (2011) expressed "organizational resilience" as a characteristic that emerges in an organization and focuses on efforts to respond to environmental turbulence and destructive events by reducing an organization's weaknesses and renewing its effectiveness (Karaköse et al., 2020, 155).

Duchkek (2014) placed "organizational resilience" on the axes of "organizational learning", knowledge management, and dynamic capabilities. Duchkek conceptualized "organizational resilience" as enterprises' ability to predict events that develop in the external world, cope with unexpected events, and learn from these through "organizational learning" (Duchkek, 2014, 144).

Although researchers have not agreed on the definition of "organizational resilience", the idea that "organizational resilience" capacity represents a dynamic capability has been frequently mentioned (Karaköse et al., 2020, 155). Additionally, diverse definitions stress the ability of organizations that possess this quality to survive by quickly grasping and coping with any situation that affects their way of doing business (Ruiz-Martin et al., 2018, 15). As a dynamic capability, "organizational resilience" means the dynamic adaptation developed in response to any unexpected situation. "Organizational resilience" expresses the ability to predict, withstand, cope with, and ultimately adapt to future adversities by recombining available resources to become stronger and more resourceful (Conz & Magnani, 2020, 407). "Organizational resilience" expresses the response, adaptation, and transformation that organizations display to economic, political, social, and environmental uncertainties and crises (Durmuş, 2025, 50). An organization's ability to recover from a disruptive event or major crisis and maintain its resilience depends on its structure, operational systems, and management processes. In this context, organizational resilience is defined as an organization's ability to anticipate potential threats, effectively cope with adverse events, and adapt to changing conditions (Duchek, 2020, 220; Al, 2025, 710).

2.2.1. Dimensions of organizational resilience

The "organizational resilience" sub-dimensions are used in diverse ways in the literature. To dimension and measure the construct, Mallak (1998) examined "organizational resilience" under six dimensions: solution-seeking, avoidance, critical understanding, role dependence, source reliance, and resource access (Kantur & İseri-Say, 2015, 458). McManus et al. (2008) examined "organizational resilience" as a three-dimensional construct: situation awareness, management of keystone vulnerabilities, and adaptive capacity. The "organizational resilience" model suggested by Lee et al. (2013) consists of four factors: resilience ethos, situation awareness, adaptive capacity, and management of keystone vulnerabilities (Al-Ayed, 2019, 180). The present research addressed "organizational resilience" capacity under three main dimensions and ten sub-dimensions, as in the study by Lengnick-Hall et al. (2011), in the form commonly used in the literature. The said dimensions

are cognitive, behavioral, and contextual resilience (Lengnick-Hall, 2011, 244).

2.2.1.1. Cognitive elements of organizational resilience

The dimension of the cognitive elements of “organizational resilience” comprises two sub-dimensions: conceptual orientation and constructive sense-making. In **conceptual orientation**, organizations can foster a positive, constructive conceptual orientation through a strong sense of purpose, core values, a genuine vision, and intentional use of language. Combined with a strong sense of core values and purpose and identity, conceptual orientation encourages an organization to establish frameworks that ensure problem-solving and action, rather than those that threaten rigidity or increase dysfunctional commitment (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011, 246). **Constructive sense-making** is organizations’ ability to interpret and make sense of new situations when faced with unfamiliar situations and circumstances (Ma et al., 2018, 252). The main idea of sense-making is that it is an achievement arising from attempts to create order in reality and retrospectively make sense of what has happened (Weick, 1993, 635). The ability to conceptualize novel and appropriate solutions determines “organizational resilience” (Amabile, 1988). Organizations that can interpret and make sense of the unexpected situations they encounter become resilient by developing ways to monitor, simulate, and use new information to predict future events from the external environment (Karaköse, 2019, 26).

2.2.1.2. Behavioral elements of organizational resilience

The behavioral elements of “organizational resilience” reveal the components of the ability to take action based on what is acquired owing to cognitive elements (Lengnick-Hall & Beck, 2005, 751). These elements are grouped under four headings: learned resourcefulness, original/unscripted agility, practical habits, and behavioral preparedness (Akgün & Keskin, 2014, 6920).

Learned resourcefulness refers to individuals’ and organizations’ ability to display do-it-yourself behaviors in order to respond to unexpected situations (Subaşı & Yıldız, 2022, 101). Originality and initiative to benefit from an emergency are combined in the said behaviors. The competencies and skills, leading to learned resourcefulness, develop with practice and experience (Lengnick-Hall, 2011, 246). **Original/unscripted** agility is the ability to pursue a course of action that differs substantially from what is considered the norm within an organization. It describes a structure that adopts unexpected and timely responses to changes in the environment that influence the

organization (Garg et al., 2019, 309). An organization must develop a broader range of competitive tactics to counter emerging unexpected situations and challenges with the increased uncertainty of the organization’s environment. Such organizations are more adept at original/unscripted agility (Miller & Chen, 1996, 432). **Practical habits** mean that resilience depends on developing beneficial, practical habits, particularly repetitive, over-learned routines providing the first reaction to an unpredictable threat (Akgün & Keskin, 2014, 6920). Practical habits correlate closely with genuine organizational values. They represent a set of values that form the basis for developing daily behaviors that transform an organization’s beliefs and intended strategies into action, based on the cognitive foundations of resilience. In case an organization develops values leading to habits of inquiry instead of assumption, routines of collaboration, and a tradition of flexibility instead of rigidity, it is more likely to act intuitively (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011, 246). **Behavioral preparedness**, as used in psychology, refers to the behavior of individuals to reduce their anxiety with certain preparedness states in the face of a threat they may encounter in the real world (Notebaert et al., 2016, 166). Likewise, for an organization to benefit from unexpected situations, it must be able to make quick assessments and adjust to a complex and rapidly changing environment that it cannot control. This cycle causes organizations to experience constant anxiety (Hammonds, 2002, 3). Hence behavioral preparedness expresses the tendency of an organization to take necessary precautions and take action against any unexpected threat before the necessity emerges (Akgün & Keskin, 2014, 6920).

2.2.1.3. Contextual elements of organizational resilience

Contextual conditions supporting resilience are based on relations in and outside the organization for facilitating effective reactions to environmental complexities. The contextual elements of “organizational resilience” are gathered under four sub-dimensions: psychological safety, deep social capital, diffused power and accountability, and broad resource networks. The aforementioned factors, when combined, foster resource supply lines and interpersonal connections, leading to the ability to act promptly under uncertain and surprising circumstances (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011, 247). **Psychological safety** represents a shared belief among employees that interpersonal risk-taking within organizations is safe. This trust originates from mutual trust and respect among employees (Edmondson, 1999, 354). In working environments where employees feel psychologically unsafe, they may be at risk of being ignorant when seeking information, inadequate when asking for help, negative when providing feedback, or unsuccessful when receiving feedback (Sevimli,

2021, 33). In case individuals perceive psychological safety, they become more willing to take the risks in question. An environment of psychological safety should be created because "organizational resilience" necessitates taking interpersonal risks (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011, 247). **Deep social capital** represents the sum of the actual and potential resources that are embedded in, obtained through, and produced from the relations that individuals or organizations possess (Gölgeci & Kuivalainen, 2020, 64). Researchers have highlighted that deep social capital develops from respectful interactions within an organizational community. Respectful interactions are ongoing, face-to-face dialogues based on honesty, trust, and self-respect (Branicki et al., 2019, 1267). As indicated by Adler and Kwon, respectful interaction creates closeness based on knowledge sharing and represents a key factor that enables collaborative perception. Thus, deep social capital offers considerable benefits in the development of contextual conditions supporting resilience (Turgut & Begenirbaş, 2014, 148). These benefits can be listed as the growth of intellectual capital with increased possibility of employee tacit knowledge sharing, facilitating resource exchange and cross-functional collaboration, and establishing a support and resource network (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011, 247).

Diffused power and accountability are related to creating "organizational resilience". Resilient organizations are usually not managed hierarchically (Baykal, 2018, 41). Management in the form of self-managed holographic structures, where each organizational member has both discretion and responsibility in achieving organizational interests and where each department is a miniature version of the entire organization, is more appropriate (Morgan, 1997). Practices, such as diffused power and accountability, which involve employee participation in decision-making, can increase resilience (Ngoc Su et al., 2021, 8). **Access to broad resource networks** represents the sum of the tangible and intangible resources an organization currently possesses or could potentially obtain. Organizations with access to broad resource networks can expand the scope of applicable actions in the face of unexpected changes and offer various interpretations for applying the said resources in alternative ways (Karaköse et al., 2020, 157).

2.3. Product Innovation

In the Turkish Language Association's dictionary, "yenilik" and "yenileşim" are given as Turkish equivalents of the word "innovation." The Guide to Foreign Words of the same organization defines innovation as the presentation of novel methods in cultural, social, and administrative environments to adapt to changing circumstances (<https://sozluk.gov.tr/>, Data accessed: May 21, 2020, Time: 16:38).

However, since both terms do not correspond to the meaning of the word "innovation," it is commonly used as "inovasyon" in Turkish.

Product innovation indicates improving the existing features of a company's products to meet customer demands. Product innovation is characterized as changes made to a product's functional features, technical specifications, and components, which will ensure easy usage (Zehir et al., 2018, 30).

In product innovation terminology, it is sufficient to define "product innovation" as developing a new product. "Product innovation" aims to make usage easy for users, enable the use of more functional products, and enhance quality of life (Besler & Tonus, 2017, 53).

According to Damanpour, "product innovation" encompasses the development and delivery of novel or considerably improved products that meet consumers' needs and expectations (Damanpour, 1996, 698). Initiatives, methods, techniques, and processes for incremental enhancements of available services and products are included in "product innovation". It encompasses making evolutionary modifications to products that use prevailing technologies and organizational capabilities (Rainey, 2015, 26). "Product innovation" is defined as the design of novel products that meet unmet current and future customer needs, exceeding their expectations, or the development or improvement of existing products in this direction (Barutçugil, 2020, 23).

"Product innovation" can be divided into two groups: goods and services innovation. Whether the elements subject to innovation are tangible or intangible is the primary reason for the distinction between goods and services innovation. Whereas products, including physical goods, are tangible, services are intangible (Özdemir & Sönmez, 2018, 19).

"Product innovation" focuses on enhancing the strategic position and product delivery capabilities of an organization via leadership and creativity. "Product innovation" involves a few important aspects:

- Investigating new product needs.
- Identifying the appropriate direction and suitability for novel products.
- Creating a suitable game plan for the whole management system for the development and commercialization of novel products.
- Choosing novel product opportunities for investment.
- Developing organizational capabilities to produce successful novel products.
- Creating novel products and performing novel product development

(Rainey, 2015, 147).

Innovation provides solutions to organizational problems, contributing to enterprise survival, market leadership, and increased profits in the long run (Örücü

et al., 2011, 62). Innovation refers to a necessity for enterprises that strive to compete in environments where change is common, unpredictable, and constant. Innovation, which forms a source of competitive advantage and therefore survival, is an essential concept for organizations in coping with alterations in the external environment (Kaya & Altındağ, 2019, 145). "Product innovation" is challenging due to the complexity of the business environment, the varying needs of customers and markets, the effect of competition, and the requirements of understanding the present and predicting the future (Rainey, 2015, 5).

Akgün and Keskin (2014) investigated the role of variables related to "organizational resilience capacity" on the innovation performance of firms and revealed that "product innovation" mediates the correlation between firm performance and resilience capacity (Akgün & Keskin, 2014). The concept of "organizational resilience", established on an organization's adaptation skills and capacity, overlaps with the dynamic capabilities theory. The initial stage in the development of dynamic capabilities theory began with Penrose in 1959 and was clarified by Barney in 1991 with the emergence of the resource-based view (Şahin&Kaplan, 2017, 106-107). When the resource-based view became insufficient to explain how today's organizations can adapt to rapidly changing environments, this inadequacy led to the emergence of dynamic capabilities theory (Kasap, 2019, 6).

Since it is possible to characterize "organizational resilience" as the ability to maintain continuity in response to environmental change, this definition expresses the level of the ability to respond to environmental uncertainty in an organizational sense, adapt to change, and adjust to alterations (Öztürk, 2018,72). Eisenhardt and Martin's definition of dynamic capabilities is as follows: Dynamic capabilities are processes by which a firm uses its resources to match, or even create, market change (specifically, the processes of integrating, restructuring, acquiring, and releasing resources). Therefore, dynamic capabilities are organizational and strategic routines that firms create to obtain new resource configurations in response to market emergence, collision, division, growth, and death (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000, 1107). In this context, the concept of organizational resilience, which is actually built upon an organization's adaptability skills and capacity, coincides with the dynamic capabilities theory. Since organizational resilience can be defined as the ability to maintain continuity in response to environmental change, this definition expresses the level of organizational ability to respond to environmental uncertainties, adapt to change, and adjust to it (Öztürk, 2018, 72). Teece et al. (1997) expressed dynamic capabilities as an enterprise's ability to build, integrate, and restructure its external and internal capabilities in order to react promptly to altering environmental conditions.

Thus, dynamic capabilities refer to the ability of an organization to obtain novel and innovative forms of competitive advantage, considering its path dependencies and market positions (Teece et al., 1997, 510).

Based on the literature, the dynamic capabilities theory effectively explains an organization's "product innovation" capabilities.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Model and Hypotheses

Studies performed to date agree on the idea that enterprises improving their organizational capabilities will achieve a competitive advantage both at present and in the future. "Organizational resilience" correlates closely with the ability and capability of an organization to return to a stable condition following a disruption. Furthermore, rather than reacting to problems with the existing product, an organization should take proactive steps and develop new products to ensure its continued development despite adversities and turbulence, offering novel and improved products. An extended ability to establish novel opportunities prior to disruptive events (e.g., anticipate novel and improved products) necessitates the dynamic aspect of resilience within the framework of "product innovation" (Akgün & Keskin, 2014, 6918).

In 1997, Teece et al. claimed that enterprises should develop dynamic capabilities to gain and sustain a competitive advantage, especially in dynamic and turbulent environmental conditions (Garcia-Morales et al., 2006, 26). In their study carried out in 2006, Garcia-Morales defined "organizational learning" and innovation as the dynamic capabilities that organizations utilize to adapt to quickly altering external environments (Garcia-Morales et al., 2006, 22). On the other hand, in their study conducted in 2000, Eisenhardt and Martin stated that "organizational learning" and superior organizational innovation are dynamic capabilities integrating and restructuring competencies to adjust to a rapidly altering external environment. They also highlighted the necessity of dynamic capabilities in adapting to quickly changing environments by arguing that dynamic capabilities represent a set of particular and definable processes, including innovation and strategic decision-making (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000, 1117).

Since the dynamic capabilities theory allows organizations to respond to environmental alterations by reshaping or adapting themselves, the dynamic capabilities theory forms the basis for the model of the current work. The conceptual model for the research is given below. The proposed model argues that "organizational resilience" fully mediates the impact of "organizational learning" on "product innovation".

Figure 1. Research Model

Research Hypotheses

- H₁: "Organizational learning" significantly and positively affects "product innovation".
- H₂: "Organizational learning" significantly and positively affects "organizational resilience".
- H₃: "Organizational resilience" significantly and positively affects "product innovation".
- H₄: "Organizational resilience" mediates the effect of "organizational learning" on "product innovation".
- H₅: The impact of "organizational learning" on "product innovation" varies according to "organizational resilience".

3.2. Research Method

The main hypothesis and sub-hypotheses were established in line with the literature review and the research model developed. To determine whether the hypotheses were supported, the study attempted to numerically reveal the relationships between the variables using a quantitative method. The main population included employees of exporting enterprises operating under the Istanbul Textile and Apparel Exporters' Association (ITKIB) in Istanbul province. Since, it was not possible to reach all registered businesses, the sample size of the study was calculated at a 95% confidence level and determined as follows. Based on a total 31,795 registered businesses in the Ready-Made Clothing/Textile/Leather sector, the valid sample size was calculated as 380. Data was collected from 382 participants for the study. Responses were collected based on a 5-point Likert scale using a survey as a data collection method. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Istanbul Beykent University Social Sciences Ethics Committee (No.060821-62).

Based on the data obtained from the study, a pilot study was conducted when the number of data reached 100. Factor analysis, validity, and reliability analyses were applied to the survey scales using the SPSS program. Data collection continued based on the results obtained from these analyses. After a number of surveys as an adequate sample size in the population were collected, factor analysis, validity and reliability analyses, correlation analyses, and

mediation and moderation analyses were applied to the conceptual model of the research using SPSS Process Macro. The data collected using the methods above yielded meaningful, valid, and reliable results. Additionally, mediation and moderation analyses were conducted using the SPSS PROCESS V.4 plugin. Afterward, the results obtained from the study were explained, and an evaluation was performed based on these results to assess the impacts of "organizational learning" and to present new theoretical and managerial recommendations that will make a contribution to the literature.

3.3. Scales Used in the Study

A comprehensive literature review on the subject was performed, paying attention to the fact that the survey scales to be used in the research were up-to-date and obtained from internationally accepted sources. Scales, which included statements consistent with the theoretical and operational definitions of the variables and whose validity and reliability had been confirmed in research conducted to date, were preferred.

For the purpose of measuring the "organizational learning" variable, the study employed a scale developed by Chiva and Alegre in 2009, whose validity and reliability studies have been conducted and which is commonly employed in the literature. This scale comprises five dimensions and 14 items. To measure the "organizational resilience" variable, the present work used a scale developed by Lengnick-Hall et al. in 2011, whose validity and reliability have been tested and which is frequently utilized in the literature. The scale in question includes three main dimensions, ten sub-dimensions, and 43 items. Two of the 43 items were excluded from the scope of the current study since they conceptually overlapped with the "Organizational Learning Capability" Scale. The 41 items of the scale were used. To measure the "product innovation" variable, the current study preferred a scale developed by Vila and Kuster in 2007, which has been tested for validity and reliability and is commonly utilized in the literature. The said scale comprises four main dimensions and 24 items. The present study used the scale's section related to the "product innovation" dimension. The "Product Innovation" Scale contains five items.

4. Results

4.1. Sampling

The frequency analysis of the demographic characteristics of the employees in the ready-to-wear/textile/leather export sector who took part in the research showed that 66.8% of the participants were female, and 33.2% were male. Of these individuals, 2.4% had a doctorate degree, 17% had a master's degree, 63.1% had a bachelor's degree, 12% had an associate degree, 4.5% had a high school degree, and 1% had a primary school degree. According to their workplace titles, 21.5% of the participants were employees, 6% were low-level managers, 47.4% were mid-level managers, and 24.9% were senior managers. Considering the participants' length of service in the sector, 57.6% have worked for 15 years and more, 16.2% for 11-15 years, 15.2% for 6-10 years, 9.2% for 1-5 years, and 1.8% have worked for less than 1 year.

In line with the statistical remedies suggested by Podsakoff et al. (2012), common method bias was assessed using Harman's single-factor test, in which all study variables were loaded onto a single factor

(Podsakoff et al., 2003, 2012). The results indicated that the single factor accounted for 47.9% of the total variance. Although this value approaches the commonly accepted threshold of 50%, it does not exceed it, suggesting that common method bias is unlikely to pose a serious threat to the validity of the study findings (Harman, 1960, 65-66).

4.2. Validity and Reliability Measures

Cronbach's alpha analysis was carried out to test the reliability of the scales employed in the research. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient is a value examined in Likert scales to determine whether the items are consistent with each other and whether these items measure a hypothetical variable (Cantolat, 2023, 2440). The analysis results in Table 1 demonstrate that Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was computed to be 0.925, 0.977, and 0.867 for the "Organizational Learning Capability" Scale, "Organizational Resilience" Scale, and "Product Innovation" Scale, respectively. These values demonstrate that the scale has internal consistency and a high level of reliability.

Table 1. Reliability Levels

Scales and Dimensions	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Organizational Learning	14	0.925
Experimentation	2	0.921
Risk Taking	2	0.814
Interaction with the external environment	3	0.794
Dialogue	4	0.849
Participative decision making	3	0.938
Organizational Resilience	38	0.977
Cognitive Dimension	10	0.945
Conceptual orientation	4	0.938
Constructive sense-making	4	0.898
Strategic sense-making	2	0.793
Behavioral Dimension	14	0.953
Original/Unscripted agility	9	0.948
Practical Habits	3	0.880
Behavioural Preparedness	2	0.849
Contextual Dimension	14	0.941
Psychological Safety	4	0.937
Deep social capital	6	0.935
Broad resource networks	4	0.928
Product Innovation	5	0.867

4.3. Exploratory Factor Analysis

The current section contains the findings of the exploratory factor analysis for the "Organizational Learning Capability," "Organizational Resilience," and "Product Innovation" scales employed in the study. Table 2 lists the values of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity, which are

statistical methods commonly utilized to assess the adequacy of the data sample. The obtained values showed that the KMO values of all study variables were above 0.8, and Bartlett's test of sphericity was also significant. The results above reveal that the study data set is appropriate for factoring. Tables 3, 4, and 5 contain the factor analysis findings.

Table 2. KMO Values and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Results for All Variables

Variables	KMO	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
		Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Organizational Learning	.903	3.791.096	91	.000
Organizational Resilience	.968	17.586.635	903	.000
Product Innovation	.823	944.677	10	.000

4.3.1. Factor analyses of the organizational learning capability scale

The factor analysis of the "Organizational Learning Capability Scale" demonstrated that the total explained variance of the five-component structure was

81.367%, and the five-component factor structure agrees with the original scale. Table 3 shows the scale structure. In line with the results in Table 3, each item on the "Organizational Learning Capability Scale" had factor loadings in the range of 0.597 - 0.856.

Table 3. Exploratory Factor Analysis of the Organizational Learning Capability Scale

Items	Factors				
	Experimen- tation	Risk Taking	Interaction with the external en- vironment	Dialogue	Participati- ve decision making
People here receive support and encouragement when presenting new ideas	.799				
Initiative often receives a favourable response here so people feel encouraged to generate new ideas	.783				
People are encouraged to take risks in this organization		.856			
People here often venture into unknown territory		.855			
It is part of the work of all staff to collect, bring back and report information about what is going on outside the company			.758		
There are systems and procedures for receiving, collating and sharing information from outside the company			.829		
People are encouraged to interact with the environment: competitors, customers, technological institutes, universities, suppliers etc			.644		
Employees are encouraged to communicate				.617	
There is a free and open communication within my work group				.847	

Managers facilitate communication				.746	
Cross-functional teamwork is a common practice here				.597	
Managers in this organization frequently involve employees in important decisions					.794
Policies are significantly influenced by the view of employees					.829
People feel involved in main company decisions					.836

4.3.2. Factor analyses of the organizational resilience scale

The factor analysis results of the “Organizational Resilience Scale” show that the total explained variance of the three-component structure was 81.241%,

and the three-component factor structure agrees with the original scale. Table 4 displays the scale structure. According to the results presented here, the factor loadings of each item on the “Organizational Resilience Scale” varied between 0.517 and 0.884.

Table 4. Exploratory Factor Analysis of the Organizational Resilience Scale

Items	Factors								
	Cognitive Dimension			Behavioral Dimension			Contextual Dimension		
	Conceptual Orientation	Constructive Sense-making	Strategic Sense-making	Original/ Unscripted Agility	Practical Habits	Behavioural Preparedness	Psychological Safety	Deep Social Capital	Broad Resource Networks
We have a strong sense of purpose, core values and a genuine vision in our organization	.706								
We have strong core values coupled with a sense of purpose and identity, which encourage us to frame conditions in ways that enable problem solving and action rather than in ways that lead to either threat rigidity or dysfunctional escalation of commitment in our organization.	.705								
We have a prevailing vocabulary that implies capability, influence, competence, consistent core values and a clear sense of direction in our organization	.709								
We have a highly visible moral purpose that enables us to motivate employees, to perceive opportunities, and to unleash physical and psychological resources in our organization.	.626								
We have an attitude that balances the contradictory forces of confidence and expertise against scepticism, caution and a search for new information in our organization.		.517							
We have a mindset that requires a solid grasp on reality and a relentless desire to question fundamental assumptions in our organization.		.586							

We have a mindset that empowers interpretation of the world and a positive perception of experiences in our organization.		.712							
We focus on situation-specific interpretations and judgements rather than programmed explanations.		.586							
We use a common language (i.e. words, images and stories) to construct meaning, describe situations, and imply both understanding and emotion in our organization.			.733						
We encourage ingenuity and look for opportunities to develop new skills rather than emphasise standardisation and the need for control.			.567						
People engage in disciplined creativity to devise unconventional, yet robust, responses to unprecedented challenges in our organization.				.543					
People combine originality and initiative to capitalise on an immediate situation in our organization.				.589					
We have an ability to follow a dramatically different course of action from that which is the norm in our organization.				.803					
People engage in non-conforming strategic repertoires (those that depart from the industry's norms) rather than simple strategic repertoires (those that tend to be preoccupied with a single type of action) to make counter-intuitive moves in our organization.				.756					
We have a complex and varied action inventory that enables us to follow a dramatically different course of action from that which is the norm in our organization.				.801					
We have a number and diversity of competitive actions available to adopt unexpected and timely responses to market shifts in our organization.				.668					
We rely on the development of useful, practical habits, especially repetitive, over-learned routines that provide the first response to any unexpected threat in our organization.				.538					
We take actions and make investments before they are needed to ensure that we are able to benefit from situations that emerge in our organization				.612					
We have the ability to spot an opportunity that other firms without our competencies might miss in our organization				.578					
We develop values that lead to traditions of flexibility rather than rigidity in our organization.					.659				
We have habits that intuitively behave in ways that open the system and create robust responses.					.518				

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We deliberately unlearn obsolete information or dysfunctional heuristics in our organization.						.874			
We quickly discard behaviours that constrain us because it is for us to develop new competencies in our organization						.746			
People perceive their work environment as being conducive to taking interpersonal risks, the risk of being seen as ignorant by asking questions or seeking information, in our organization.							.844		
People perceive their work environment as being conducive to taking interpersonal risks, the risk of being seen as incompetent as a result of asking for help, admitting mistakes or experimenting, in our organization.							.884		
People perceive their work environment as being conducive to taking interpersonal risks, the risk of being seen as negative when offering critical feedback, in our organization.							.878		
People perceive their work environment as being conducive to taking interpersonal risks, the failure to seek feedback for fear of imposing on someone's time or goodwill, in our organization.							.864		
We have respectful interactions within an organisational community.								.700	
We have face-to-face, ongoing dialogues rooted in trust, honesty and self-respect.								.739	
We have informed and disclosure-oriented intimacy								.648	
People exchange resources as they recognise their interdependence.								.758	
People have an orientation and are able to share tacit information.								.678	
We have cross-functional collaboration in our organization.								.752	
People forge relationships with others who can share key resources.									.555
We use relationships with supplier contacts and strategic alliances to secure needed resources to support adaptive initiatives.									.652
We ensure that bonds with various environmental agents are maintained, thereby reinforcing social capital beyond the firm's boundaries.									.659
We promote organizational slack									.595

In the component of cognitive resilience, a new dimension was formed by separating two questions from the "constructive sense-making" sub-dimension. This dimension was named "strategic sense-making." In the component of behavioral resilience, all questions (2 questions) from the "Learned resourcefulness" sub-dimension and 2 questions from the

"Behavioral preparedness" sub-dimension were combined into the "Original/unscripted agility" dimension. One question was deleted from the "Practical habits" sub-dimension; thus, 3 questions remained in this sub-dimension. Two questions remained in the "Behavioral preparedness" sub-dimension. The component of contextual resilience was elimi-

nated since the 4 questions in the "Diffused power and accountability" sub-dimension were deleted. In the article from which the scale was developed and adopted, unlike the initial design, the variables of conceptual orientation, constructive sensemaking, learned resourcefulness, psychological safety, and dispersed power and accountability were combined into a single factor. The factor structure obtained in the current study differs significantly from the sample from which the scale was developed. This is due to two main reasons: (i) differences in context and sample, (ii) methodological choices, and more stringent item-elimination criteria. In the current study's sample, two items from "constructive sensemaking" clustered separately because they captured a forward-looking, goal-vector framing rather than immediate interpretive processes, forming a new and theoretically consistent dimension called "strategic sensemaking." In behavioral resilience, the items from "learned resourcefulness" and two items from "behavioral preparedness" merged into a single factor of "extraordinary agility," reflecting common behavioral patterns such as rapid trial-and-error under uncertainty, generating solutions with scarce

resources, and quickly exploiting windows of opportunity. In contrast, the "Distributed Power and Responsibility" items did not support the factor structure due to low variance/distinctiveness and weak loadings/community in the organizational context of the current sample and were removed from the model based on analytical criteria. All these decisions were justified by exploratory factor analysis and loading threshold checks. Consequently, the model demonstrates a higher fit with theoretical expectations and the statistical properties of the data.

4.3.3. Factor analyses of the product innovation scale

The factor analysis results of the "Product Innovation Scale" demonstrate that the total explained variance of the single-component structure was 65.945%, and the factor structure consisted of a single component, in line with the original scale. Table 5 displays the scale structure. According to the results in Table 5, the factor loadings of each item on the "Product Innovation Scale" ranged from 0.736 to 0.851.

Table 5. Exploratory Factor Analysis of the Product Innovation Scale

Items	Factors
Superiority(&/ordifferentiation) over other competing products	.851
Degree to which the product adapts to customer needs/tastes	.846
Degree to coherence between product price and the result it brings	.736
Perceived technological sophistication of the product	.811
Perceived novelty/originality of the product	.810

4.3. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis

Pearson's correlation analysis was performed to make sense of the correlations between the overall scale scores and the sub-dimension variables in the study. Correlation analysis is employed to identify the strength and direction of the linear correlation between two variables. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) can take positive or negative values between -1 and +1 (Pallant, 2020, 144). As specified by

Mukaka (2012), the correlation coefficient (r) varying between 0 and 0.3 represents a "weak" correlation; the correlation coefficient that varies between 0.3 and 0.5 means a "low" correlation; the correlation coefficient in the range of 0.5-0.7 displays a "moderate" correlation; the correlation coefficient ranging from 0.7 to 0.9 refers to a "high" correlation; the correlation coefficient varying between 0.9 and 1 represents a "very high" correlation (Mukaka, 2012, 71). This study evaluated correlation coefficients based on the study by Mukaka (2012).

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis

Variables	N	Mean	Std. D.	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
Organizational Learning (1)	382	3.77	.775	1										
Experimentation (2)	382	4.15	.899	.809**	1									

Risk Taking (3)	382	3.20	1.06	.656**	.460**	1								
Interaction with the external environment(4)	382	3.67	1.06	.815**	.592**	.441**	1							
Dialogue (5)	382	4.04	.777	.843**	.650**	.452**	.541**	1						
Participative decision making (6)	382	3.63	1.08	.860**	.648**	.421**	.609**	.674**	1					
Organizational Resilience(7)	382	3.90	.744	.879**	.754**	.482**	.669**	.792**	.790**	1				
Cognitive Dimension(8)	382	3.95	.824	.860**	.755**	.443**	.677**	.765**	.770**	.944**	1			
Behavioral Dimension (9)	382	3.86	.820	.840**	.734**	.455**	.678**	.705**	.766**	.952**	.876**	1		
Contextual Dimension (10)	382	3.87	.736	.787**	.647**	.461**	.539**	.777**	.699**	.926**	.815**	.798**	1	
Product Innovation (11)	382	4.21	.669	.571**	.541**	.204**	.461**	.513**	.533**	.663**	.609**	.671**	.584**	1

**p<0,05

As seen in Table 6, all correlations between the overall scale scores and all sub-dimension variables, both among themselves and with each other, were significant. There was a statistically significant positive and moderate correlation (r=.571**) between the “Organizational Learning Capability Scale” and the “Product Innovation Scale”. A statistically significant positive and high correlation (r=.879**) was identified between the “Organizational Learning Capability Scale” and the “Organizational Resilience Scale”. It can also be stated that there was a statistically significant positive and moderate correlation (r=.663**) between the “Organizational Resilience Scale” and the Product Innovation scale. Hypotheses H1, H2, and H3 were accepted based on the findings presented above.

The research found that the average for the “Organizational Learning Capability Scale” was 3.77 ± .775, the average for the “Organizational Resilience

Scale” was 3.90 ± .774, and the average for the “Product Innovation Scale” was 4.21 ± .669. The scales’ average values were computed by dividing the sum of the sample data by the sample size and finding a single value representing the sample in the best way. The value of standard deviation is found by taking the square root of the mean of the squared deviations from the mean. The said value shows the data’s closeness to the mean. The obtained results demonstrate that our data were close to the mean and were homogeneously distributed.

4.4. Regression Analyses

In this part of the study, linear regression analyses were conducted to reveal the effects of independent variables on dependent variables and the results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Regression Analysis Results of the Effect of Independent Variables on Dependent Variables

H	Model	N	β	Std. Error	Std. β	p	F	Adjusted R2	Result
H ₁	1 OL→PI	382	0,492	0,036	0,571	0,000**	183,950	0,324	Supported
H ₂	2 OL→OR	399	0,844	0,024	0,879	0,000**	1287,610	0,772	Supported
H ₃	3 OR→PI	399	0,596	0,034	0,663	0,000**	298,195	0,438	Supported

OL=Organizational Learning; OR=Organizational Resilience; PI=Product Innovation; *p<0,05 **p<0,01

When the results of Model 1 in Table 7 are examined, it is seen that the established model is statistically significant (F-statistic = 183.950; p = 0.000). According to the model results, 32.4% of the change in product innovation is explained by organizational learning (R2 = 0.324). A 1-unit increase in organizational learning increases product innovation by 0.571 units (Beta = 0.571). Hypothesis H1 is supported.

When the results of Model 2 are examined, it is seen that the established model is statistically significant (F-statistic = 1287.610; p = 0.000). According to the model results, 77.2% of the change in organizational resilience is explained by organizational learning (R2 = 0.772). A 1-unit increase in organizational learning increases organizational resilience by 0.879 units (Beta = 0.879). Hypothesis H2 is supported.

When the results of Model 3 are examined, it is seen that the established model is statistically significant (F-statistic = 298.195; p = 0.000). According to the model results, 43.8% of the change in product innovation is explained by organizational resilience (R2

= 0.438). A 1-unit increase in organizational learning increases organizational resilience by 0.663 units (Beta = 0.663). Hypothesis H3 is supported.

4.5. Mediation and Moderation Analyses

Mediation and moderation analyses were carried out with the SPSS PROCESS V.4 plugin. The mediation analysis was examined using Model 4, whereas the moderation analysis was examined by utilizing Model 1. In line with the test of Hayes, the indirect impact of X on Y significantly indicates the mediation variable. Confidence intervals present the findings. There is a significant mediation effect when a zero value is absent between the BootULCI and BootLLCI values (Hayes, 2022). There is no p-value in the model in question (Çelik & Uzunçarşılı, 2023, 13). In this test, the confidence level for all confidence intervals in the output is 95.0000, whereas 5.000 is the number of bootstrap samples for the percentile bootstrap confidence intervals.

Table 8. Mediation Analysis

Hypothesis	Model 4	Effect Type	Coeffc	Boot Se	t	p	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI	Result
H ₄	OL*OR-PI	Total Effect	.492	.036	13,563	.000	.421	.564	Supported (Full mediation effect)
		Direct Effect	-.044	.069	629	.530	-.180	.093	
		Indirect Effect	.622	.070			.483	.756	

As seen in Table 8, during the analysis, the independent variable (X) of "Organizational Learning" (OL) and the independent variable (Y) of "Product Innovation" (PI) were taken as the mediators (M) of "Organizational Resilience" (OR) in Model 4. In the model testing Hypothesis H4, the BootLLCI value was 0.483, and the BootULCI value was 0.756. No zero was found between the two values. Moreover, since P = .0530 > .05, the effect became insignificant, and it was concluded that there was a full mediation variable. Hypothesis H4 was accepted in line with these findings. "Organizational Resilience" (OR) fully me-

diates the impact of "Organizational Learning" (OL) on "Product Innovation" (PI).

The moderation analysis was initiated after this point. The primary goal of the moderation analysis is to discover how the variable selected as a moderator impacts the strength of the correlation between the independent and dependent variables (Conbolat, 2023, 2441). In the above-mentioned test, similar to the mediation test, the confidence level for all confidence intervals in the output is 95.0000, while 5.000 is the bootstrap sample size for percentile bootstrap confidence intervals. The results in Table

Table 9. Moderation Analysis

Hypothesis	Model 1	Effect Type	Coeffc	Boot Se	t	p	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI	Result
H ₅	OL*OR-PI	Constant	2.051	.425	4.825	.000	1.215	2.887	Not Supported
		OL(X)	-.096	.156	-.620	.536	-.402	.209	
		OR(W)	.594	.132	4.500	.000	.334	0.853	
		Int_1	.014	.036	.0379	.705	-.058	.085	

Note: R2 = .440; R2-chng= .000; P=.705 > .05, Se.: Standard Error

9 demonstrate that all predictor variables included in the regression analysis explained approximately 44% ($R^2=.440$) of the variance in "product innovation". According to the results of the test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s), $R\text{-sq}= .440$; $R^2\text{-chnge}= .000$. Additionally, since $P=.705 > .05$, it

was concluded that there was no moderator variable. The findings above indicate that hypothesis H5 was rejected. Hence the effect of "Organizational Learning" (OL) on "Product Innovation" (PI) does not vary according to "Organizational Resilience" (OR).

Table 9. Hypothesis Test Results and Acceptance-Rejection Table

H₁	"Organizational learning" significantly and positively affects "product innovation".	Supported
H₂	"Organizational learning" significantly and positively affects "organizational resilience".	Supported
H₃	"Organizational resilience" significantly and positively affects "product innovation".	Supported
H₄	"Organizational resilience" mediates the impact of "organizational learning" on "product innovation".	Supported (full mediation effect)
H₅	The effect of "organizational learning" on "product innovation" varies with "organizational resilience".	Not Supported (Moderator Effect)

5. Conclusion

The present work investigated how the effects of the "organizational learning capabilities" of employees working in textile and apparel exporting enterprises in Istanbul province during crisis periods on "product innovation" varied according to "organizational resilience". "Organizational learning capabilities" increase knowledge capacity. Since "organizational learning capabilities" enhance creative performance and support adaptation to the external environment, they contribute to a more realistic prediction of potential opportunities and threats caused by environmental uncertainty and change (Örmeci & Öcal, 2023, 33; Özer Targalöz, 2024, 335).

Hence the present research concentrated on "organizational learning capabilities", in particular. The study results showed that "organizational learning capabilities" significantly and positively affect "product innovation" in these enterprises. In this respect, the research results are similar to those of a study conducted by Örmeci and Öcal in 2023 which also found a positive and significant relationship between organizational learning capabilities and technological innovation capabilities. The findings of the research conducted by Özdevecioğlu and Biçkes on the 500 largest and the second 500 largest industrial enterprises of Turkey in 2015 also reveal that there is a significant and positive relationship between organizational learning and innovation. Also, Migdadi (2021) found in his study, examining the relationships between organizational learning ability, innovation, and organizational performance in service sector enterprises in Jordan (2021), that organizational learning ability affects innovation.

While some studies in the literature report that export leads to innovation or R&D expenditures, others assert that the correlation between export and innovation is bidirectional. Since the impact of "organizational learning capabilities" on "product innovation" was going to be assessed, the study

specifically included exporting enterprises. Because the export firms are more intensely exposed to innovation processes that improve their performance. In addition, the effect of "organizational learning" on "product innovation" and the intensity and direction of the said impact vary according to "organizational resilience". The variation in this impact according to "organizational resilience" will cause differences in "product innovation" capacities in companies with different levels of "organizational resilience". The obtained findings indicated a highly significant, positive relationship between "organizational learning capabilities" and "organizational resilience". In other words, "organizational learning" positively affects "organizational resilience".

Orth and Schuldis (2021) also found, in their study which is investigating the impact of organizational learning abilities and inability to learn of enterprises, on their "organizational resilience" during the Covid-19 pandemic that "organizational learning capability" of enterprises had a positive effect on "organizational resilience". It is essential that enterprises have skills, such as learning capability and resilience, to display a positive performance and maintain their current position, particularly in crisis environments and under volatile market conditions. As a result of the analyses conducted in the study, the "Distributed Power and Responsibility" dimension of organizational resilience was removed from the scale based on statistical criteria. However, this situation may also reflect the contextual characteristics of the study's sample. It is expected that exporting firms will tend to centralize their operational processes by providing tighter control in order to respond quickly to crises. Under these conditions, the distribution of power and responsibility may be perceived as risky. Centralized leadership structures are more common in cultural contexts with high power distances, especially under conditions of uncertainty. Therefore, the lack of empirical support for this dimension may indicate a context-specific manifestation of organi-

zational resilience during crises, rather than a conceptual inadequacy of the structure. According to the general research findings, "organizational resilience" also positively affects "product innovation". Parallel to the findings above, empirical and theoretical research has also shown that resilient organizations preserve sufficient flexibility, adaptability, and creativity for survival in a business environment where intense competition and chaos prevail (Chen, Liu, & Zhou, 2021, 48899, Cited by: Tolay & Güler-yüz, 2022, 3033). Furthermore, the research results indicated that "organizational resilience" fully mediates the impact of "organizational learning" on "product innovation", and the effects of "organizational learning" on "product innovation" do not vary according to the level of "organizational resilience". No matter how high the learning capability of enterprises may be, the transformation of accumulated knowledge into innovation during crisis periods depends critically on the establishment of a resilient organizational structure. Without such resilience, learning remains a valuable resource, yet its potential to generate innovative outcomes cannot be fully realized under conditions of heightened uncertainty. From a dynamic capabilities perspective, organizational resilience can be viewed as a higher-order capability that enables organizations to reconfigure and mobilize learning-based resources, thereby sustaining innovation in turbulent environments.

The findings obtained also agree with the dynamic capabilities theory, which we used as the basis. The dynamic capabilities theory argues that enterprises should develop and renew their innovative cultures and innovation capacities to increase their "organizational resilience". Kozcu and Özmen (2023) had seen that in their study which is investigating both the indirect effect of organizational learning ability on organizational performance through the mediating effect of organizational resilience and the direct effect of organizational learning ability on organizational performance in the manufacturing sector, taking into account the moderating effect of market turbulence, there is no direct positive effect of organizational learning ability on organizational performance and no indirect effect of organizational learning ability on organizational performance through organizational resilience.

As can be seen, numerous studies exist in both domestic and international literature investigating the correlation between "organizational learning" and "innovation". While very few, there are also studies investigating the effects of these two variables, or different variables, on "organizational resilience". However, no research exists in any sector investigating how the impact of organizational learning capabilities on product innovation varies according to organizational resilience. However, it is crucial for export sector companies, particularly those most affected by the crisis, to develop their organizational

resilience during such periods. This further enhances the significance of this study.

It is believed that the findings of the present work make a contribution to relevant theory and research in this respect. The proactive strategies of exporting enterprises, in particular, significantly contribute to their performance. Accordingly, it would be beneficial for managers of export enterprises operating in the textile sector in Istanbul province, who participated in the research, to adapt to variable and uncertain environmental conditions by taking the initiative. In the textile and apparel export sector, the findings suggest that managers can enhance organizational resilience through practical measures such as increasing supply chain flexibility and investing in digitalization. Practices including supplier diversification, closer coordination with logistics partners, and data-driven production planning help transform organizational learning into product innovation during crisis periods. Such practices are particularly critical in the textile and apparel industry, where short product life cycles, volatile demand, and global supply chain dependencies intensify the need for resilience-driven innovation. By improving "organizational learning capabilities" through diverse practices in enterprises, it is possible to impact the innovation levels of enterprises by increasing their "organizational resilience". This, in turn, will positively and indirectly affect the performance of enterprises.

The fact that the research was done solely on employees of export enterprises operating under the Istanbul Textile and Apparel Exporters' Association (ITKIB) in Istanbul province constitutes its limitation. Furthermore, the literature review found no similar studies using all the variables in this study together. Conducting future research with different sample groups and in more dynamic and diverse sectors, e.g., the finance sector, may contribute to the results. Moreover, the model can be expanded by including different variables, such as performance and sustainability. The research data were collected through a survey, and the findings were analyzed by employing different techniques. It would be beneficial to examine the subject with different research methods in terms of contribution to sector professionals and academia.

The research results support the existing literature on the relationship between organizational learning and product innovation, and contribute to the literature due to the paucity of existing studies on the relationship between organizational learning and organizational resilience. The study is entirely original in its examination of the impact of organizational resilience on product innovation, the impact of organizational learning on product innovation, and the mediating and moderating roles of organizational resilience, and aims to offer a new perspective for future research.

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